

Greenhouse gas implications of mobilizing agricultural biomass for energy: A re-assessment of global potentials in 2050 under different food-system pathways

– Supplementary material –

Gerald KALT^{a,1}, Christian LAUK^a, Andreas MAYER^a, Michaela C. THEURL^a,
Katrín KALTENEGER^b, Wilfried WINIWARTER^{b,c}, Karl-Heinz ERB^a,
Sarah MATEJ^a, Helmut HABERL^a

a) Institute of Social Ecology (SEC),
Department of Economics and Social Sciences,
University of Natural Resources & Life Sciences, Vienna (BOKU)
1070 Vienna, Schottenfeldgasse 29, Austria

b) International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA)
Schlossplatz 1, A-2361 Laxenburg, Austria

c) Institute of Environmental Engineering,
University of Zielona Góra,
Licealna 9, PL 65-417 Zielona Góra, Poland

1) Corresponding author; gerald.kalt@boku.ac.at, +43 1 47654-73744

Content

1	World regions	1
2	Methods: Calculation of emissions from carbon stock changes	1
2.1	Calculation of soil carbon stocks	3
2.1.1	General approach	3
2.1.2	Relationship between grazing intensity and soil carbon stocks.....	4
2.1.3	Relationship between residue removal and soil carbon stocks	4
2.2	Tillage practices in world regions.....	5
2.3	Distribution of agricultural land	6
2.3.1	World regions and ecological zones	6
2.3.2	World regions, soil types and climate zones.....	7
3	Model input data	10
3.1	Agricultural land by world region.....	10
3.2	Livestock distribution	10
3.3	Crop yields	11
3.4	Diets.....	11
4	Results	13
4.1	Biomass potentials by world regions	13
4.2	GHG cost curves for energy crops excluding opportunity GHG costs	14
4.3	Numerical scenario results	14
4.3.1	Bioenergy potentials and GHG costs.....	14
4.3.2	Agricultural land use 2050	17
4.3.3	CO ₂ emissions resulting from land-use change	21
	Literature.....	25

1 World regions

The regional grouping (Figure S1) is adopted from previous studies (e.g. Erb et al., 2016a; Haberl et al., 2011) and is based on the classification of the macro-geographical (continental) regions and geographical sub-regions as defined by the United Nations Statistical Division.

Figure S1. Regional grouping (own illustration based on Haberl et al., 2011)

2 Methods: Calculation of emissions from carbon stock changes

We calculate carbon emissions from land-use change (LUC) using a 'stock difference approach' largely based on IPCC default data (IPCC, 2006): The basic approach is to determine net CO₂ emissions to or removals from the atmosphere (i.e. CO₂ sinks) by calculating the difference in natural carbon stocks on each unit area undergoing LUC:

$$EMI_{Cstock} = -\frac{44}{12} \cdot \Delta C = -\frac{44}{12} \cdot \frac{C_{t2} - C_{t1}}{t_2 - t_1}, \quad (1)$$

EMI_{Cstock} denotes net CO₂ emissions in tons per year, ΔC annual carbon stock change per unit area in tons C per year, and C_{t1} and C_{t2} the carbon stocks at time t_1 and t_2 , respectively. 44/12 is the ratio of molecular weights of CO₂ and C and the change in sign is due to the convention that negative emissions represent decreases in C stocks, i.e. emissions to the atmosphere.

The considered types of land-use change are:

- Conversion of grassland to cropland and vice versa
- Conversion of cropland and highly productive grassland to energy plantations
- Vegetation regrowth on grassland and cropland without any management (natural succession)¹

¹ In IPCC (2006), "natural forests" also comprise natural vegetation in ecological zones like shrubland or steppe (see Table 4.12). To be consistent with IPCC Guidelines and indicate that natural succession does not necessarily imply reforestation, we use the terms "natural forests" and "natural vegetation" synonymously.

Since deforestation is disregarded (see section 2.1 of the main article), LUC from forest to agricultural land is not taken into account. Loss of agricultural land to infrastructure and settlement areas is basically considered in BioBaM; corresponding carbon stock changes are, however, disregarded due to their limited relevance, vast uncertainties regarding carbon stocks in infrastructure and settlement area, and the fact that they are identical across all scenarios.

Figure 2 illustrates the relevant types of LUC, underlying mechanisms and the respective C stock changes. Following IPCC (2006) accounting principles, we consider the C pools soil, above- and below-ground biomass and dead organic matter (litter; deadwood is disregarded). $\Delta C_{\text{soil/biomass/litter}}$ denotes stock changes in the respective C pool associated with the respective type of LUC. Since litter is assumed to be zero on cropland as well as grassland under Tier 1 (IPCC, 2006), ΔC_{litter} is zero in case of LUC between these two land categories. For energy crops, we assume regionally specific litter stocks according to Kalt et al. (2019).

On grassland, soil C stocks are influenced by the level of degradation (IPCC Tier 1 approach). We here assume that the level of degradation is correlated to the grazing intensity, measured as grazing harvest in per cent of actual net primary production (Erb et al., 2016b; see below).

Figure 2: Relevant types of land-use change and associated C stock changes

Following IPCC default methods, natural carbon stocks in different land-use types, and therefore also the values of ΔC_{soil} , $\Delta C_{\text{biomass}}$, ΔC_{litter} in case of LUC depend on various site-specific parameters. We use global raster data on the distribution of agricultural land and site conditions, to determine C stock values for each raster cell. Based on this, we calculate average C stocks for every land-use type and world region. The distributions of agricultural land types among climate zones, soil types and ecological zones are provided in section 2.3. Table S1 gives an overview of the IPCC data tables used for deriving average C stock values. Further assumptions (due to insufficient data on global scale) are also summarized here.

Table S1. Data basis for calculating world regional-specific C stocks for different land-use types and C pools in accordance with IPCC guidelines 2006, with according tables referring to IPCC (2006). The relevant site conditions (climate, soil and/or ecological conditions) are specified in brackets.

C pool	Land-use types			Further assumptions
	Cropland	Grassland	Natural forest / natural vegetation	
	Table 2.3 (soil types ¹ , climate zones ¹)			
Soil	Table 5.5 (climate zones ¹ , tillage level ²)	Table 6.2 (climate zones ¹ , degradation level ³)	– (no further influencing factors than soil type and climate zone)	Cropland: Medium input level (see Table 5.5) is assumed as global default
Biomass	5 t C/ha (Table 5.9 IPCC Guidelines 2006)	Table 6.4 (climate zones ¹)	Table 4.12 (ecological zones ⁴)	Belowground biomass in forests is assumed to be 30 % of aboveground biomass
Litter	– (no litter)	– (no litter)	Table 2.2 (climate zones ¹ , forest types)	Deadwood in natural forest is neglected (no default values available), therefore litter is the only relevant fraction of dead organic matter

Comments:

- 1) Raster data on soil types and climate zones: JRC (2018)
- 2) Assumed tillage levels are based on Prestele et al. (2018) (see below; Table S2)
- 3) Degradation levels are assumed to be correlated with grazing intensities (see below)
- 4) Raster data on ecological zones: FAO (2012)

Transition times from initial carbon stocks to a new equilibrium state extend over decades or even more than a century (in case of forest). For soil and litter carbon stocks, we assume the default 20 years according to IPCC Tier 1 methods. This implies that the emissions in 2050 depend on the timing of land-use changes during the timeframe from 2012 to 2050, and that the snapshot of land-use change emissions in 2050 is of limited significance. Therefore, we consider the total cumulative carbon stock changes during 2012 to 2050 and assume constant annual rates of land-use change during this timeframe. Since GHG costs generally refer to emissions or savings per year (see section 2.1), cumulative C stock changes are converted to average annual CO₂ emissions.

2.1 Calculation of soil carbon stocks

2.1.1 General approach

Under IPCC Tier 1, SOC stocks depend on the type of land use, site-specific ecological parameters (soil types, climate) and – in case of agricultural land – further influencing parameters like tillage practices and inputs of residues or livestock manure. Using Tier 1 default parameters, SOC stocks are calculated from climate- and soil-specific reference values SOC_{REF} given in tons of C per ha and dimensionless “stock change factors” that depend on the land-use system (F_{LU}), the management regime (F_{MG}) and input levels (F_I). For a homogenous patch of 1 hectare, the SOC stock is calculated using the following equation (based on equation 2.25 in (IPCC, 2006)),

$$SOC = SOC_{REF} \cdot F_{LU} \cdot F_{MG} \cdot F_I \quad (2)$$

The IPCC Tier 1 default values for SOC_{REF} are provided in Table 2.3, the stock change factors for cropland in Table 5.5 and for grassland in Table 6.2 in IPCC (2006). For forest, all stock change factors under Tier 1 are equal to 1, hence SOC generally corresponds to SOC_{REF} .

In our model, this calculation is relevant for determining ΔC_{soil} for changes in broad land-use classes, changes in residue removal rates on cropland and changes in grazing intensities on grazing land. The latter two are explained in detail in the following sub-sections.

2.1.2 Relationship between grazing intensity and soil carbon stocks

For modelling the impact of grazing on SOC stocks on grassland, we assume a linear relation between grazing intensity (measured as ratio of grazed or mowed biomass to actually prevailing net primary production; Erb et al., 2016a; Haberl et al., 2007) and degradation levels (modelled as management factor F_{MG}). For non-degraded grassland F_{MG} is 1. Since F_{LU} and F_I are also equal to 1 for grazing land (see Table 6.2 in IPCC, 2006), SOC stocks correspond to the soil- and climate-specific reference values SOC_{REF} . For moderately degraded grassland, the management factor ($F_{MG}^{mod.degr.}$) ranges from 95 % to 97 %, depending on the climate zone. Hence, moderate degradation corresponds to a reduction of SOC by 3 to 5 %.

We assume that grassland with zero grazing/mowing (grazing intensity = 0) is non-degraded, and that the maximum sustainable grazing intensity (GI_{max} ; see Erb et al., 2016a) corresponds to the degradation level “moderate”. Between zero grazing and maximum sustainable grazing a linear decrease of SOC is assumed (Figure S3). Severely degraded grassland is not considered in this approach, because grazing beyond the maximum sustainable intensity is generally ruled out in our model (see section 2.1 of the main article).

Figure S3: Assumed relationship between grazing intensity and soil organic carbon on grazing land

2.1.3 Relationship between residue removal and soil carbon stocks

Our approach for modelling the impact of crop residue removal on SOC is based on the “Input factor” F_I . Four levels of input are distinguished for cropland: “Low”, “Medium”, “High without manure” and “High with manure” (Table 5.5 in IPCC, 2006). We assume that crop residues removal up to 20 % corresponds to the level “High without manure”. For removal rates between 20 and 60 %, we assume a linear relation between the residue removal rate and the input factor, with 60 % corresponding to the input level “Low”. Figure S4 illustrates this assumption.

The management factor F_{MG} is also relevant for cropland because it varies for different tillage levels (see next sub-section), and is therefore also included in the y-axis markings in Figure S4. The land use factor F_{LU} is omitted here because for “long-term cultivated cropland” it is equal to 1.

Figure S4: Assumed relationship between residue removal rate and soil organic carbon on cropland

2.2 Tillage practices in world regions

According to IPCC methods (IPCC, 2006), SOC stocks on cropland are influenced by tillage practices through the management factor F_{MG} . To estimate global SOC stocks on cropland, we use literature data on tillage (shares of “conservation agriculture”) per country and derive shares for the three tillage levels for each world region. Table S2, based on Prestele et al. (2018), summarizes the assumed tillage shares.

In the scenarios we assume these shares to remain constant until 2050.

Table S2. Assumed shares of full, reduced and zero tillage for estimating SOC stocks

Region	Zero tillage	Reduced tillage	Full tillage
Northern Africa and Western Asia	0.2%	0.0%	99.8%
Sub-Saharan Africa	0.7%	0.2%	99.1%
Central Asia and Russian Federation	4.0%	1.0%	95.0%
Eastern Asia	5.9%	1.5%	92.7%
Southern Asia	0.8%	0.2%	99.0%
South-Eastern Asia	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%
Northern America	27.3%	9.2%	63.5%
Latin America & the Caribbean	33.9%	5.5%	60.6%
Western Europe	3.4%	19.8%	76.8%
Eastern & South-Eastern Europe	2.3%	5.9%	91.8%
Oceania and Australia	37.1%	9.3%	53.6%

Source: Kalt et al. (2019), based on Prestele et al. (2018)

2.3 Distribution of agricultural land

2.3.1 World regions and ecological zones

The following tables show the distribution of cropland, highly productive (class 1) grazing land and other grazing land² in each world region across ecological zones, as derived from the respective GIS data (ecological zones: (FAO, 2012), soil types and climate zones: (JRC, 2018), agricultural land: (Erb et al., 2007)). These distributions, together with annual biomass growth data (Table 4.12 in IPCC, 2006), determine biomass accumulation and maximum carbon stocks in each world region.

Table S3. Distribution of cropland across ecological zones (own calculations)

	Northern Africa and Western Asia	Sub-Saharan Africa	Central Asia and Russian Federation	Eastern Asia	Southern Asia	South-Eastern Asia	Northern America	Latin America & the Caribbean	Western Europe	Eastern & South-Eastern Europe	Oceania and Australia
Tropical rainforest	0.0%	17.2%	0.0%	0.0%	3.3%	60.8%	0.0%	19.9%	0.0%	0.0%	0.8%
Tropical moist forest	0.0%	24.5%	0.0%	0.9%	13.2%	13.1%	0.3%	32.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Tropical dry forest	0.0%	20.4%	0.0%	0.0%	24.2%	19.8%	0.0%	11.7%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%
Tropical shrubland	0.0%	19.4%	0.0%	0.0%	35.7%	0.4%	0.0%	0.3%	0.0%	0.0%	2.5%
Tropical desert	6.4%	1.1%	0.0%	0.0%	8.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%
Tropical mountain system	2.4%	11.9%	0.0%	0.3%	0.6%	5.6%	0.0%	10.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.7%
Subtropical humid forest	1.3%	1.2%	0.0%	41.8%	0.6%	0.2%	13.6%	12.8%	0.0%	0.0%	2.6%
Subtropical dry forest	27.6%	1.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.6%	0.9%	31.6%	1.8%	12.8%
Subtropical steppe	26.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	3.0%	0.0%	8.6%	5.4%	0.0%	0.0%	66.3%
Subtropical desert	4.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.2%	1.7%	0.0%	0.0%	2.2%
Subtropical mountain system	25.3%	3.1%	0.1%	7.4%	9.6%	0.1%	0.2%	2.5%	6.5%	0.1%	0.0%
Temperate oceanic forest	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.1%	46.8%	1.5%	6.7%
Temperate continental forest	5.2%	0.0%	38.8%	22.3%	0.2%	0.0%	22.3%	0.0%	4.1%	75.7%	0.0%
Temperate steppe	0.0%	0.0%	25.7%	10.2%	1.0%	0.0%	44.0%	1.7%	0.0%	16.8%	0.0%
Temperate desert	1.1%	0.0%	7.5%	2.2%	0.1%	0.0%	1.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Temperate mountain system	0.4%	0.0%	6.1%	14.7%	0.1%	0.0%	3.5%	0.0%	5.5%	4.1%	5.0%
Boreal coniferous forest	0.0%	0.0%	15.8%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	4.7%	0.0%	4.6%	0.0%	0.0%
Boreal tundra woodland	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Boreal mountain system	0.0%	0.0%	6.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.9%	0.0%	0.0%

² In BioBaM each grazing class is actually characterized by a specific distribution rather than the aggregate distribution of grazing classes 2 to 4 shown in Table S5.

Table S4. Distribution of grazing land (class 1) across ecological zones (own calculations)

	Northern Africa and Western Asia	Sub-Saharan Africa	Central Asia and Russian Federation	Eastern Asia	Southern Asia	South-Eastern Asia	Northern America	Latin America & the Caribbean	Western Europe	Eastern & South-Eastern Europe	Oceania and Australia
Tropical rainforest	0.0%	8.2%	0.0%	0.0%	9.2%	55.4%	0.0%	13.8%	0.0%	0.0%	3.4%
Tropical moist forest	0.0%	14.7%	0.0%	0.4%	16.6%	22.4%	0.2%	42.5%	0.0%	0.0%	1.0%
Tropical dry forest	0.0%	25.5%	0.0%	0.0%	20.1%	15.8%	0.0%	12.3%	0.0%	0.0%	6.0%
Tropical shrubland	0.0%	35.2%	0.0%	0.0%	27.7%	0.8%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	17.3%
Tropical desert	3.5%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	6.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	14.7%
Tropical mountain system	1.2%	13.8%	0.0%	0.9%	0.8%	5.2%	0.0%	8.7%	0.0%	0.0%	1.2%
Subtropical humid forest	8.6%	0.2%	0.0%	16.9%	0.0%	0.2%	8.3%	19.8%	0.0%	0.0%	9.1%
Subtropical dry forest	19.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.5%	0.4%	21.6%	1.7%	4.4%
Subtropical steppe	2.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	2.2%	0.0%	9.2%	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	19.8%
Subtropical desert	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%
Subtropical mountain system	45.6%	2.1%	0.0%	17.6%	15.4%	0.1%	0.4%	0.4%	1.3%	0.0%	0.0%
Temperate oceanic forest	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.6%	0.9%	67.9%	1.1%	13.0%
Temperate continental forest	10.2%	0.0%	32.3%	18.1%	0.0%	0.0%	15.2%	0.0%	3.1%	77.9%	0.0%
Temperate steppe	0.0%	0.0%	49.8%	13.7%	0.0%	0.0%	59.9%	0.3%	0.0%	16.5%	0.0%
Temperate desert	1.0%	0.0%	2.6%	0.8%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Temperate mountain system	8.5%	0.0%	5.3%	30.2%	1.8%	0.0%	2.3%	0.2%	2.8%	2.7%	9.7%
Boreal coniferous forest	0.0%	0.0%	4.9%	0.7%	0.0%	0.0%	2.9%	0.0%	1.7%	0.0%	0.0%
Boreal tundra woodland	0.0%	0.0%	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Boreal mountain system	0.0%	0.0%	4.6%	0.7%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	1.4%	0.0%	0.0%

Table S5. Distribution of grazing land (classes 2, 3 and 4) across ecological zones (own calculations)

	Northern Africa and Western Asia	Sub-Saharan Africa	Central Asia and Russian Federation	Eastern Asia	Southern Asia	South-Eastern Asia	Northern America	Latin America & the Caribbean	Western Europe	Eastern & South-Eastern Europe	Oceania and Australia
Tropical rainforest	0.0%	10.1%	0.0%	0.0%	1.4%	45.1%	0.0%	10.7%	0.0%	0.0%	1.5%
Tropical moist forest	0.0%	21.1%	0.0%	0.2%	1.5%	23.5%	0.3%	13.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%
Tropical dry forest	0.0%	15.8%	0.0%	0.0%	2.9%	12.6%	0.0%	12.2%	0.0%	0.0%	7.0%
Tropical shrubland	0.0%	38.5%	0.0%	0.0%	5.1%	0.7%	0.0%	1.5%	0.0%	0.0%	8.3%
Tropical desert	23.9%	8.4%	0.0%	0.0%	12.3%	0.0%	0.0%	1.5%	0.0%	0.0%	15.5%
Tropical mountain system	4.1%	3.5%	0.0%	0.3%	0.4%	17.5%	0.0%	17.7%	0.0%	0.0%	0.7%
Subtropical humid forest	0.2%	0.4%	0.0%	8.3%	0.2%	0.5%	3.5%	3.6%	0.0%	0.0%	2.2%
Subtropical dry forest	6.1%	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.8%	0.7%	22.7%	11.7%	1.3%
Subtropical steppe	30.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	22.9%	0.0%	14.5%	15.1%	0.3%	0.0%	19.5%
Subtropical desert	11.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	9.3%	0.0%	12.3%	8.0%	0.0%	0.0%	41.0%
Subtropical mountain system	21.1%	1.7%	0.1%	12.4%	40.1%	0.3%	3.4%	4.5%	2.0%	0.4%	0.0%
Temperate oceanic forest	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	1.9%	14.5%	0.8%	1.1%
Temperate continental forest	1.1%	0.0%	2.2%	4.8%	0.1%	0.0%	5.1%	0.0%	3.0%	61.2%	0.0%
Temperate steppe	0.0%	0.0%	15.5%	14.9%	2.6%	0.0%	12.7%	9.0%	0.0%	16.1%	0.0%
Temperate desert	1.5%	0.0%	41.8%	20.5%	0.1%	0.0%	23.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Temperate mountain system	0.6%	0.0%	6.4%	37.2%	1.1%	0.0%	8.5%	0.7%	7.6%	9.9%	1.8%
Boreal coniferous forest	0.0%	0.0%	11.9%	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	5.2%	0.0%	20.4%	0.0%	0.0%
Boreal tundra woodland	0.0%	0.0%	7.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	6.3%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%
Boreal mountain system	0.0%	0.0%	15.1%	1.0%	0.0%	0.0%	4.1%	0.0%	29.5%	0.0%	0.0%

2.3.2 World regions, soil types and climate zones

The following table presents the climate-soil matrices for cropland, class 1-grazing land and other grazing land for all world regions; that is, the shares of the respective agricultural land type located in each combination of climate- and soil-type.

Greenhouse gas implications of mobilizing agricultural biomass for energy:
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Table S6. Distribution of agricultural land across climate zones and soil types (own calculations)

Climate / Soil type →	Cropland							Grazing land class 1							Grazing land class 2,3 and 4						
	organic	sandy	wetland	volcanic	spodic	high act. clay	low act. clay	organic	sandy	wetland	volcanic	spodic	high act. clay	low act. clay	organic	sandy	wetland	volcanic	spodic	high act. clay	low act. clay
Northern Africa and Western Asia																					
warm temperate moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	2.2%	0.8%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	5.8%	3.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.1%
warm temperate dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	55.0%	1.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	28.6%	0.4%	0.0%	0.4%	0.9%	0.0%	0.0%	34.0%	0.1%
cool temperate moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	4.2%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	34.7%	0.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	4.1%	0.0%
cool temperate dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	6.4%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	14.1%	0.3%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	8.9%	0.0%
boreal moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
boreal dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical montane	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.8%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	3.9%	0.0%
tropical wet	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical dry	0.0%	1.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	26.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	11.7%	0.1%	0.0%	2.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	44.3%	0.0%
Sub-Saharan Africa																					
warm temperate moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	1.2%	1.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.6%	0.7%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.4%
warm temperate dry	0.0%	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	4.8%	2.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	2.7%	1.1%	0.0%	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	5.5%	0.8%
cool temperate moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%
cool temperate dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
boreal moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
boreal dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical montane	0.1%	2.6%	0.3%	0.2%	0.0%	8.6%	10.4%	0.0%	5.0%	0.9%	0.4%	0.0%	15.7%	6.4%	0.1%	8.6%	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	7.4%	5.7%
tropical wet	0.0%	0.1%	0.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.7%	3.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.5%	1.9%	0.0%	0.1%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.6%
tropical moist	0.0%	0.9%	0.3%	0.0%	0.0%	7.0%	18.7%	0.0%	1.3%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	4.0%	9.3%	0.0%	2.6%	0.5%	0.0%	0.0%	6.3%	14.1%
tropical dry	0.1%	9.4%	0.9%	0.0%	0.0%	18.8%	7.5%	0.0%	10.2%	1.1%	0.0%	0.0%	26.8%	9.4%	0.1%	15.5%	0.8%	0.0%	0.0%	26.5%	2.9%
Central Asia and Russian Federation																					
warm temperate moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
warm temperate dry	0.0%	0.3%	1.1%	0.0%	0.0%	8.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	3.9%	0.0%	0.0%	1.9%	1.0%	0.0%	0.0%	13.1%	0.0%
cool temperate moist	1.9%	0.1%	0.4%	0.0%	14.0%	16.4%	0.2%	0.8%	0.0%	0.7%	0.1%	5.3%	13.5%	0.4%	0.6%	0.0%	0.1%	0.1%	1.9%	2.3%	0.0%
cool temperate dry	0.2%	0.7%	2.2%	0.0%	0.0%	39.8%	0.2%	0.1%	0.2%	2.0%	0.0%	0.0%	58.4%	0.1%	0.0%	0.3%	1.9%	0.0%	0.0%	36.8%	0.0%
boreal moist	0.7%	0.0%	1.4%	0.0%	3.5%	4.4%	0.0%	0.5%	0.0%	0.6%	0.0%	0.9%	4.9%	0.0%	4.0%	0.0%	7.5%	0.3%	8.5%	11.8%	0.0%
boreal dry	0.2%	0.0%	0.6%	0.0%	0.6%	2.2%	0.0%	0.1%	0.1%	0.5%	0.0%	0.2%	6.4%	0.0%	0.3%	0.1%	1.7%	0.0%	0.5%	5.3%	0.0%
tropical montane	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical wet	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Eastern Asia																					
warm temperate moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.3%	0.0%	18.8%	5.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.5%	0.4%	0.0%	11.0%	3.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	5.4%	2.3%
warm temperate dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.2%	0.1%	22.6%	1.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.1%	0.0%	16.9%	1.9%	0.0%	0.3%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	9.4%	0.3%
cool temperate moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.4%	0.0%	7.4%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.7%	0.3%	0.1%	14.3%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.1%	0.0%	5.7%	0.0%
cool temperate dry	0.0%	1.6%	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	23.1%	0.0%	0.0%	1.7%	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	31.2%	0.0%	0.0%	8.1%	1.1%	0.0%	0.0%	42.2%	0.0%
boreal moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.0%	0.2%	2.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.1%	1.6%	0.0%
boreal dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.3%	0.0%	0.1%	7.9%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.4%	0.0%	0.7%	17.6%	0.0%
tropical montane	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.8%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.3%
tropical wet	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical moist	0.0%	0.1%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	5.8%	8.9%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.9%	2.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.4%	1.9%
tropical dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Southern Asia																					
warm temperate moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	1.3%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.5%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.6%	0.1%
warm temperate dry	0.0%	0.1%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	7.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.5%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	39.1%	0.0%
cool temperate moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	6.3%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.9%	0.0%
cool temperate dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	3.2%	0.2%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	9.3%	0.0%
boreal moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.5%	0.0%
boreal dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.0%
tropical montane	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.7%	0.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.6%	0.2%	0.0%	1.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	7.5%	0.2%
tropical wet	0.0%	0.1%	1.6%	0.0%	0.0%	1.4%	2.1%	0.0%	0.4%	2.2%	0.0%	0.0%	3.1%	7.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.6%	1.2%
tropical moist	0.1%	0.5%	1.8%	0.0%	0.0%	19.9%	9.3%	0.1%	1.3%	1.8%	0.0%	0.0%	17.7%	12.3%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	2.9%	1.6%
tropical dry	0.0%	0.7%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	45.2%	5.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	36.3%	1.7%	0.0%	0.7%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	31.2%	0.3%
South-Eastern Asia																					
warm temperate moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.4%	0.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.3%	0.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	1.8%	2.0%
warm temperate dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
cool temperate moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.0%
cool temperate dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
boreal moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
boreal dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical montane	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.5%	0.0%	0.5%	3.7%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.0%	0.5%	2.7%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.7%	0.0%	1.6%	11.1%
tropical wet	4.1%	1.5%	5.2%	1.4%	0.0%	10.4%	32.9%	3.8%	2.6%	4.4%	1.5%	0.0%	11.1%	26.6%	4.2%	1.3%	2.5%	0.8%	0.0%	8.7%	21.3%
tropical moist	0.0%	0.3%	4.1%	0.5%	0.0%	8.0%	22.9%	0.6%	0.5%	5.0%	0.7%	0.0%	10.9%	22.8%	0.6%	0.3%	2.4%	0.5%	0.0%	6.9%	32.0%
tropical dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.5%	0.0%	0.0%	1.9%	0.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.9%	0.0%	0.0%	2.8%	1.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.5%

Greenhouse gas implications of mobilizing agricultural biomass for energy:
A re-assessment of global potentials in 2050 under different food-system pathways

Table S6 (continued). Distribution of agricultural land across climate zones and soil types (own calculations)

↓Climate / Soil type →	Cropland							Grazing land class 1						Grazing land class 2,3 and 4							
	organic	sandy	wetland	volcanic	spodic	high act. clay	low act. clay	organic	sandy	wetland	volcanic	spodic	high act. clay	low act. clay	organic	sandy	wetland	volcanic	spodic	high act. clay	low act. clay
Northern America																					
warm temperate moist	0.0%	0.1%	1.4%	0.0%	0.0%	11.3%	9.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.8%	0.0%	0.0%	11.3%	9.8%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	1.8%	3.8%
warm temperate dry	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	10.5%	0.1%	0.0%	0.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	17.3%	0.1%	0.0%	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	27.6%	0.1%
cool temperate moist	0.4%	0.8%	0.9%	0.1%	3.8%	20.2%	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.8%	0.1%	3.8%	9.9%	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.4%	0.1%	0.4%	4.7%	0.4%
cool temperate dry	0.1%	0.6%	0.7%	0.1%	0.0%	28.1%	0.0%	0.0%	3.8%	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	37.5%	0.0%	0.1%	0.5%	0.2%	0.1%	0.0%	32.9%	0.1%
boreal moist	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	1.1%	0.2%	2.4%	0.0%	1.9%	4.4%	0.0%
boreal dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	1.3%	0.0%	0.1%	1.7%	0.0%
tropical montane	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.0%
tropical wet	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical moist	0.3%	0.7%	1.1%	0.0%	0.0%	1.7%	2.8%	0.2%	0.3%	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.8%	0.9%	0.1%	0.1%	0.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.6%
tropical dry	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	4.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	3.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	6.8%	0.0%
Latin America & the Caribbean																					
warm temperate moist	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.5%	0.0%	3.2%	0.7%	0.0%	0.2%	0.1%	0.5%	0.0%	5.4%	1.1%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	1.9%	0.4%
warm temperate dry	0.0%	0.3%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	14.9%	0.0%	0.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	9.5%	0.0%	0.0%	1.2%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	24.5%	0.1%
cool temperate moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.9%	0.1%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	3.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.0%	5.1%	0.8%
cool temperate dry	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	2.8%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.0%	0.7%	0.0%	13.9%	0.2%
boreal moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
boreal dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical montane	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.0%	4.7%	0.6%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	2.0%	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	6.5%	0.2%
tropical wet	0.0%	0.3%	1.0%	0.3%	0.0%	3.5%	6.9%	0.0%	0.6%	1.3%	0.2%	0.0%	2.5%	5.4%	0.1%	0.8%	1.8%	0.2%	0.0%	2.3%	3.4%
tropical moist	0.1%	2.2%	1.9%	0.3%	0.0%	15.7%	22.7%	0.0%	3.7%	3.0%	0.1%	0.0%	14.2%	30.2%	0.1%	1.0%	2.0%	0.0%	0.0%	5.6%	7.1%
tropical dry	0.0%	0.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.0%	3.1%	0.0%	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	8.4%	5.5%	0.0%	1.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	15.6%	2.1%
Western Europe																					
warm temperate moist	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	17.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.1%	0.5%	0.0%	0.0%	20.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	6.2%	0.0%
warm temperate dry	0.0%	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	36.9%	0.4%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	23.6%	0.4%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	24.0%	0.2%
cool temperate moist	1.9%	0.4%	2.1%	0.0%	8.3%	26.5%	0.1%	3.0%	0.5%	5.8%	0.3%	7.5%	33.0%	0.2%	5.7%	0.3%	1.8%	1.2%	17.2%	27.8%	0.3%
cool temperate dry	0.2%	0.2%	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	3.8%	0.0%	0.2%	0.1%	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	2.7%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.7%	0.0%
boreal moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.2%	0.0%	1.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	8.6%	3.2%	0.0%
boreal dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical montane	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical wet	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.8%	0.0%
Eastern & South-Eastern Europe																					
warm temperate moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	2.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	3.4%	0.1%	0.0%	0.1%	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	10.8%	0.0%
warm temperate dry	0.2%	0.5%	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	20.1%	0.3%	0.1%	0.5%	0.5%	0.0%	0.0%	19.1%	0.5%	0.7%	0.6%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	18.9%	0.5%
cool temperate moist	1.9%	0.9%	1.2%	0.1%	14.2%	24.0%	0.1%	1.7%	0.4%	1.5%	0.0%	11.7%	25.1%	0.1%	2.1%	0.5%	1.4%	0.2%	9.5%	28.1%	0.1%
cool temperate dry	0.8%	1.0%	0.9%	0.0%	0.0%	30.6%	0.2%	0.9%	0.7%	0.9%	0.0%	0.0%	31.9%	0.2%	0.3%	0.6%	0.3%	0.0%	0.0%	24.5%	0.2%
boreal moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
boreal dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical montane	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical wet	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Oceania and Australia																					
warm temperate moist	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.9%	0.0%	2.8%	1.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	2.2%	0.0%	6.6%	3.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	1.2%	0.9%
warm temperate dry	0.0%	3.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	51.1%	15.3%	0.1%	0.8%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	15.0%	9.3%	0.0%	1.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	13.8%	1.8%
cool temperate moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	1.3%	0.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	9.8%	1.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.6%	0.1%
cool temperate dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.8%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
boreal moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
boreal dry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
tropical montane	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.7%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.0%
tropical wet	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.5%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	2.0%	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.8%	0.1%
tropical moist	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.5%	1.2%	0.0%	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.8%	2.0%
tropical dry	0.0%	2.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	16.7%	2.4%	0.0%	6.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	31.5%	6.1%	0.0%	14.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	57.4%	2.4%

3 Model input data

In the following sections, selected input data to BioBaM is presented, namely the distribution of agricultural land and the shares of livestock in indoor housing and intensive systems.

3.1 Agricultural land by world region

Table S7. Distribution of agricultural land in the base year 2012 (based on Erb et al., 2007 and 2016a); updated to 2012 using data from FAO (2019) and Potapov et al. (2017)

10 ⁶ hectare	Northern Africa and Western Asia	Sub-Saharan Africa	Central Asia and Russian Federation	Eastern Asia	Southern Asia	Southeast Asia	Northern America	Latin America	Western Europe	Eastern & Southeastern Europe	Oceania and Australia	World
Cropland	72.1	243.1	159.8	132.0	238.3	113.2	205.7	188.9	83.4	84.9	49.8	1,571.3
Grazing land class 1	8.9	252.5	77.1	126.0	22.5	41.7	117.3	284.5	52.6	46.5	47.1	1,076.7
Grazing land class 2	1.4	209.6	48.6	36.0	6.6	36.2	57.3	179.8	19.9	5.0	37.4	638.0
Grazing land class 3	21.0	136.2	111.5	146.2	30.6	4.7	54.4	50.2	14.4	5.1	92.7	667.1
Grazing land class 4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1,643.8

3.2 Livestock distribution

The shares of livestock in indoor housing and intensive systems are influencing parameters on the realizability of manure potentials.

Table S8. Assumed shares of livestock in indoor housing and intensive systems

	Northern Africa and Western Asia	Sub-Saharan Africa	Central Asia and Russian Federation	Eastern Asia	Southern Asia	Southeast Asia	Northern America	Latin America & the Caribbean	Western Europe	Eastern & Southeastern Europe	Oceania and Australia	Reference; comments
Assumed share of indoor housing												
Ruminants	33.8%	33.8%	46.2%	41.6%	48.9%	39.2%	35.2%	51.5%	58.6%	57.8%	9.1%	based on GAINS database (Amann et al., 2011; Winiwarter et al., 2018)
Monogastrics	95.9%	90.5%	94.3%	91.8%	97.9%	99.6%	88.7%	83.2%	94.5%	95.4%	94.2%	
Assumed shares of intensive systems												
Ruminants	8.1%	1.7%	1.2%	0.2%	1.5%	1.1%	80.6%	35.6%	28.9%	9.3%	56.9%	based on Lowder et al. (2016); farms > 10 ha used as proxy for intensive farming
Pigs	5.6%	21.0%	59.5%	74.3%	8.1%	8.1%	59.5%	17.1%	59.5%	29.3%	69.0%	
Poultry	57.4%	29.1%	85.9%	90.1%	29.7%	29.7%	85.9%	63.5%	85.9%	47.6%	78.8%	based on Robinson et al. (2011)

Sources: Amann et al. (2011), Lowder, Scoet, & Raney (2016); Robinson et al. (2011); Winiwarter, Höglund-Isaksson, Klimont, Schöpp, & Amann (2018)

3.3 Crop yields

The following table summarizes the average crop yields derived from FAO (2018) and assumed in the scenario calculations.

Table S9. Crop yields in the base year 2012 and in 2050 according to the three scenarios

Unit: tonnes dry matter per hectare		World Regions										
		Northern Africa and Western Asia	Sub-Saharan Africa	Central Asia and Russian Federation	Eastern Asia	Southern Asia	South-Eastern Asia	Northern America	Latin America & the Caribbean	Western Europe	Eastern & South-Eastern Europe	Oceania and Australia
2012	Cereals	2.4	1.2	1.7	5.0	2.5	3.6	5.3	3.4	5.1	3.2	1.9
	Roots	5.6	2.5	3.3	4.7	5.0	5.5	8.9	3.5	8.5	3.8	3.6
	Sugarcrops	13.7	9.8	9.3	11.7	11.2	11.9	13.6	12.5	17.4	10.6	12.8
	Pulses	1.2	0.5	1.2	1.4	0.6	1.1	1.9	0.9	2.0	1.7	1.9
	Oilcrops	0.8	1.0	1.1	2.1	1.2	4.8	2.4	2.4	1.8	1.8	1.6
	Vegetables and fruits	1.4	1.2	1.1	1.4	1.3	1.5	2.5	2.3	1.6	0.9	1.8
	Other crops	1.8	0.6	1.9	2.7	1.4	0.7	2.3	1.2	1.2	1.4	2.9
BAU (2050)	Cereals	3.2	1.7	2.5	5.9	3.7	5.1	6.6	5.3	6.3	4.3	2.4
	Roots	7.5	3.3	5.1	6.4	6.5	8.1	11.3	4.5	11.7	5.2	4.7
	Sugarcrops	16.6	11.4	15.5	16.0	14.3	14.7	15.5	14.9	21.7	16.1	14.6
	Pulses	1.5	1.0	1.5	1.8	0.9	1.9	2.7	1.2	2.7	2.1	2.6
	Oilcrops	1.0	1.4	1.7	3.0	1.5	6.1	3.2	3.2	2.4	2.6	2.3
	Vegetables and fruits	2.0	1.7	1.5	1.9	1.8	2.0	3.2	2.9	2.0	1.2	2.4
	Other crops	2.3	0.7	2.3	4.1	2.0	0.9	2.9	1.6	1.5	1.6	3.3
SSS (2050)	Cereals	2.8	1.5	2.4	6.0	3.4	4.7	6.5	4.9	6.3	4.0	2.4
	Roots	6.8	2.9	4.9	6.4	5.1	6.8	10.9	3.9	11.6	4.9	4.6
	Sugarcrops	16.3	10.4	17.2	18.4	13.3	14.0	16.5	14.6	24.0	18.3	15.6
	Pulses	1.4	0.9	1.4	1.7	0.8	1.6	2.4	1.1	2.5	2.0	2.5
	Oilcrops	0.9	1.3	1.8	3.0	1.4	5.8	3.1	2.8	2.3	2.3	2.3
	Vegetables and fruits	1.8	1.5	1.4	1.9	1.6	1.9	3.2	2.8	1.9	1.2	2.4
	Other crops	2.3	0.7	2.2	4.2	1.9	1.2	3.0	1.4	1.5	1.6	3.0
TSS (2050)	Cereals	2.7	1.5	2.3	5.4	3.2	4.6	5.1	4.8	4.9	3.4	1.9
	Roots	6.6	3.0	4.8	5.9	5.5	7.5	8.8	4.1	9.4	4.3	4.1
	Sugarcrops	15.5	10.8	14.6	15.0	13.2	14.0	13.2	14.5	19.2	14.5	12.0
	Pulses	1.3	0.9	1.4	1.7	0.8	1.7	2.0	1.1	2.0	1.7	2.2
	Oilcrops	0.8	1.3	1.6	2.7	1.4	5.7	2.5	2.9	1.9	2.0	2.0
	Vegetables and fruits	1.7	1.5	1.4	1.7	1.7	1.9	2.6	2.7	1.6	1.0	2.1
	Other crops	2.3	0.7	2.2	3.7	1.8	1.2	2.3	1.5	1.2	1.3	2.9

Source: own calculations based on FAO (2018)

3.4 Diets

The following table summarizes the per-person demand of food crops and animal products (meat, dairy products, eggs etc.) in the assumed diets derived from FAO (2018) (2012, BAU, SSS, TSS) and Willett *et al* (2019) (“healthy reference diet”). Values refer to household consumption; due to losses, there is a difference between actual food intake and household consumption. For converting intake recommendations according to Willett *et al* (2019) to household level, we used loss factors according to Gustavsson *et al.* (2011). Differences between world regions in cereal consumption in the “healthy reference diet” are due to different shares of rice and conversion from paddy to milled rice. The category “other crops”, containing crops like coffee or tea, is not represented in the reference diet according to Willett *et al* (2019). Although these crops might not be required for a healthy diet, we assumed the corresponding per-person demand of the TSS scenario.

Table S10. Crop and animal products demand for food per person and year in the base year (2012) and 2050 in the different scenarios

Unit: kg dry matter per person and year		Region											
		Northern Africa and Western Asia	Sub-Saharan Africa	Central Asia and Russian Federation	Eastern Asia	Southern Asia	South-Eastern Asia	Northern America	Latin America & the Caribbean	Western Europe	Eastern & South-Eastern Europe	Oceania and Australia	
2012	Cereals	177.9	112.8	138.2	186.7	163.1	197.1	114.2	121.0	110.3	136.8	72.8	
	Roots	7.4	51.4	21.9	18.4	5.5	9.6	15.2	16.9	17.2	23.1	12.3	
	Sugarcrops	29.2	10.8	34.1	9.2	24.0	19.5	66.6	40.8	39.8	37.7	36.2	
	Pulses	6.2	8.6	0.7	1.5	8.9	2.4	4.1	10.0	3.1	2.4	1.5	
	Oilcrops	14.1	12.4	10.2	14.8	11.4	17.9	30.6	16.7	22.3	12.1	19.9	
	Vegetables and fruits	25.3	7.6	11.2	18.4	10.6	12.0	27.2	19.3	29.2	16.3	19.3	
	Other crops	5.3	2.1	3.2	2.0	2.5	2.2	10.1	5.1	12.5	4.2	6.0	
	Ruminant meat	4.9	3.3	8.3	3.1	1.7	1.4	19.5	11.4	10.3	5.1	20.3	
	Pigs, poultry, eggs	7.6	2.5	12.2	24.2	1.3	8.5	42.3	18.3	35.5	23.9	20.6	
	Milk and milk products	10.2	3.6	19.6	2.1	8.4	1.8	33.0	14.1	32.2	22.9	20.0	
	Seafood, aquatic products	2.6	2.3	4.3	13.2	1.6	8.2	6.5	2.5	6.8	3.1	5.4	
BAU (2050)	Cereals	204.3	167.4	137.2	153.0	176.5	195.8	114.2	122.2	114.9	130.8	157.8	
	Roots	10.4	58.5	22.2	16.1	8.2	12.5	14.7	14.7	15.7	24.0	33.1	
	Sugarcrops	52.7	23.9	51.9	12.9	37.8	30.7	51.7	60.2	50.6	53.3	84.1	
	Pulses	7.6	17.5	1.6	1.6	12.8	3.6	5.6	11.5	2.8	2.4	8.8	
	Oilcrops	20.9	18.7	15.7	18.3	14.4	21.6	35.6	20.3	24.5	16.9	56.4	
	Vegetables and fruits	28.0	25.5	23.5	38.0	15.8	20.8	26.3	24.2	24.5	20.1	27.6	
	Other crops	5.4	3.1	4.4	3.0	3.0	3.6	10.5	4.5	10.2	5.3	12.1	
	Ruminant meat	7.3	6.1	12.5	4.8	2.1	2.9	17.7	12.8	10.7	4.6	24.6	
	Pigs, poultry, eggs	18.2	9.4	30.8	48.2	4.3	22.4	50.2	31.9	45.2	42.9	53.3	
	Milk and milk products	11.1	4.5	17.7	3.8	10.3	2.0	26.0	13.5	27.4	20.9	24.4	
	Seafood, aquatic products	2.8	3.8	3.1	10.5	1.6	8.8	4.8	2.1	5.3	2.4	9.8	
SSS (2050)	Cereals	214.7	172.3	145.1	166.2	178.2	214.0	117.7	124.8	118.4	134.8	161.6	
	Roots	10.7	57.9	22.5	16.2	8.2	12.5	14.8	14.6	15.8	24.2	33.2	
	Sugarcrops	53.0	23.1	50.6	15.2	42.4	32.1	49.1	64.1	48.1	53.9	83.9	
	Pulses	7.9	16.9	1.6	1.6	13.2	3.5	5.6	10.9	2.8	2.4	8.2	
	Oilcrops	21.9	18.5	15.7	21.1	14.8	22.1	37.5	20.8	26.0	17.9	57.8	
	Vegetables and fruits	29.7	24.4	24.8	40.4	16.7	21.4	26.6	23.0	24.7	20.7	26.7	
	Other crops	6.0	3.3	4.9	3.7	3.4	4.1	11.4	5.7	11.2	6.1	14.0	
	Ruminant meat	7.9	5.2	12.8	5.0	2.1	3.0	18.9	13.0	11.5	4.8	26.2	
	Pigs, poultry, eggs	19.4	7.8	31.6	50.3	4.4	22.9	53.7	32.4	48.9	46.3	56.5	
	Milk and milk products	11.3	4.5	17.6	3.8	10.2	2.0	27.0	13.6	28.4	21.6	25.3	
	Seafood, aquatic products	2.9	3.2	3.1	10.5	1.6	8.6	4.9	2.0	5.4	2.5	9.7	
TSS (2050)	Cereals	205.4	167.4	137.1	149.6	179.1	187.2	113.0	124.7	110.3	127.4	153.4	
	Roots	9.9	61.0	22.0	15.9	8.2	12.6	14.5	14.3	15.4	23.9	32.2	
	Sugarcrops	49.6	24.5	48.8	9.6	41.7	32.0	41.4	55.0	41.5	48.2	75.3	
	Pulses	7.4	18.7	1.6	1.5	13.7	3.8	5.4	11.1	2.7	2.4	9.7	
	Oilcrops	20.9	19.5	15.4	14.7	14.7	22.3	34.8	19.1	23.3	15.7	56.5	
	Vegetables and fruits	28.7	28.3	23.2	38.8	16.9	22.0	24.1	26.7	22.2	20.0	25.6	
	Other crops	5.4	3.3	4.5	2.3	3.3	4.0	9.0	4.7	9.1	5.1	11.2	
	Ruminant meat	6.1	6.0	11.3	3.8	2.1	2.9	13.3	11.7	7.9	4.0	18.5	
	Pigs, poultry, eggs	14.8	8.5	26.6	38.8	4.2	22.0	37.4	28.6	33.5	33.2	40.8	
	Milk and milk products	10.9	4.3	17.0	3.7	10.1	2.0	24.7	12.9	26.3	18.5	22.9	
	Seafood, aquatic products	2.4	4.1	3.0	9.3	1.6	9.6	4.0	2.1	4.4	2.2	9.0	
Healthy ref. diet (2050)	Cereals	107.0	109.5	105.1	118.1	124.4	138.8	105.2	108.7	105.0	104.7	105.4	
	Roots	4.8	4.8	4.8	4.8	4.8	4.8	4.8	4.8	4.8	4.8	4.8	
	Sugarcrops	13.1	13.5	12.9	13.4	13.5	13.5	13.2	13.5	12.9	12.9	13.5	
	Pulses	41.6	41.6	41.6	41.6	41.6	41.6	41.6	41.6	41.6	41.6	41.6	
	Oilcrops	22.8	22.8	22.8	22.8	22.8	22.8	22.8	22.8	22.8	22.8	22.8	
	Vegetables and fruits	26.1	26.1	26.1	26.1	26.1	26.1	26.1	26.1	26.1	26.1	26.1	
	Other crops	5.4	3.3	4.5	2.3	3.3	4.0	9.0	4.7	9.1	5.1	11.2	
	Ruminant meat	3.7	3.7	3.7	3.7	3.7	3.7	3.7	3.7	3.7	3.7	3.7	
	Pigs, poultry, eggs	9.8	9.8	9.8	9.8	9.8	9.8	9.8	9.8	9.8	9.8	9.8	
	Milk and milk products	13.3	13.3	13.3	13.3	13.3	13.3	13.3	13.3	13.3	13.3	13.3	
	Seafood, aquatic products	6.2	6.2	6.2	6.2	6.2	6.2	6.2	6.2	6.2	6.2	6.2	

Source: own calculations based on FAO (2018), Willet et al. (2019) and Gustavsson et al. (2011)

4 Results

The following sections provide detailed results for the scenarios on the level of world regions.

4.1 Biomass potentials by world regions

Figure S5. Biomass potentials by world regions (TSS = Towards sustainability; SSS = Stratified societies; "BAU healthy = BAU with healthy reference diet)

4.2 GHG cost curves for energy crops excluding opportunity GHG costs

Figure S6. GHG cost curves for energy crops excluding opportunity GHG cost

4.3 Numerical scenario results

This section provides detailed tabular summaries of the scenarios results: bioenergy potentials and GHG costs for each world region and scenario (sub-section 4.3.1), agricultural land use in 2050 (4.3.2) and CO₂ emissions resulting from land-use change (4.3.3).

4.3.1 Bioenergy potentials and GHG costs

The main results of this analysis – bioenergy potentials and GHG costs – are summarized in the following table. Note that GHG costs of energy plantations include “opportunity GHG costs”, resulting from the foregone opportunity of vegetation regrowth on agricultural land. Direct GHG costs are negative because establishing energy plantations (perennial crops) on cropland or grazing land results in C stock gains (see lines “Direct GHG costs only (Opportunity GHG costs excluded)”).

By default, the mechanisms described in Fig. 2 (main article) are assumed, i.e. vegetation regrowth occurs on less productive areas because highly productive areas are considered unlikely to be abandoned and re-/afforested. This results in different areas being used for energy plantations in the “bioenergy case” than being freed up for vegetation regrowth in the “regrowth case”, because more highly productive area remains available for food and feed production in the “regrowth case”.

For illustrative purposes we also calculated the GHG costs of energy crops under the assumption that regrowth occurs on the same areas where energy crops are cultivated. This

results in different (usually lower) GHG costs for energy plantations, as Table S11 shows (see lines “GHG costs – Energy plantations”; “Sensitivity analysis: Regrowth on highly productive sites”). The global weighted average GHG costs in this case are in the range of 35% to 60% of those under default assumptions. On world regional level ranges are much larger, and GHG costs in the sensitivity analysis are sometimes even higher than under the default assumption. The reasons for these counterintuitive results are different carbon accumulation dynamics (biomass growth, changes in SOC etc.) on highly and less productive agricultural areas (see influencing parameters described in section 2), and the fact that the area of less productive grazing land being freed up per unit area of highly productive grazing land being intensified to the maximum sustainable level varies significantly between regions (see data provided in the next section).

Table S11. Bioenergy costs potentials and GHG costs in all world regions and globally

Units:
 Potentials: EJ/yr
 GHG costs: Mt CO₂e/EJ

		Northern Africa and Western Asia		Sub-Saharan Africa		Central Asia and Russian Federation		Eastern Asia		Southern Asia		South-Eastern Asia		Northern America		Latin America & the Caribbean		Western Europe		Eastern & South-Eastern Europe		Oceania and Australia		World	
BAU (2050)	Potentials - Energy crops	No grazing intensification	0.0	0.0	1.2	0.0	0.0	7.2	3.9	0.7	0.3	5.0	1.0	19.4											
		Grazing intensification on highly productive sites	0.0	0.0	4.5	1.5	0.0	11.6	7.9	20.3	0.7	7.9	2.7	57.1											
		Universal grazing intensification	0.0	0.0	5.6	5.5	0.0	13.0	10.7	32.8	4.3	8.8	4.0	84.7											
	GHG costs - Energy crops	No grazing intensification				30.8			19.8	24.9	20.2	29.8	27.7	20.3	23.8										
		Direct GHG costs only (opportunity GHG costs excluded)				-12.2			-7.6	-10.9	-7.0	-9.0	-8.0	-5.7	-8.6										
		Grazing intensification on highly productive sites				79.5	294.4		23.0	39.0	28.3	125.6	20.5	48.9	55.0										
		Sensitivity analysis: Regrowth on highly prod.sites				28.9	40.3		19.5	23.1	21.0	31.2	27.7	21.3	23.2										
		Direct GHG costs only (opportunity GHG costs excluded)				-3.8	-0.7		-4.9	-5.8	-0.6	-4.2	-5.2	-2.6	-3.2										
		Universal grazing intensification				95.9	124.8		21.8	35.6	20.4	23.7	19.4	42.1	47.3										
	GHG costs - Energy crops	Sensitivity analysis: Regrowth on highly prod.sites				28.8	40.3		19.5	22.7	21.1	32.1	27.7	21.5	24.0										
		Direct GHG costs only (opportunity GHG costs excluded)				-0.6	-0.1		-4.3	-4.0	-0.4	-1.7	-4.7	-1.0	-1.8										
	Potentials - Crop residues	40% residue removal rate	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.6	0.1	0.2	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.2	0.1	3.2											
		60% residue removal rate	0.8	3.5	1.2	3.4	3.2	1.5	2.1	2.3	1.4	0.8	0.3	20.4											
	GHG costs - Crop residues	40% residue removal rate	11.9	49.4	29.7	17.0	21.0	11.9	16.3	12.1	20.0	21.1	9.9	19.6											
		60% residue removal rate	12.1	23.7	25.2	17.8	12.5	12.8	16.5	12.7	19.9	19.6	9.8	17.2											
	Potentials: Manure	Manure from intensive systems	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.9	0.1	0.1	1.5	1.6	0.4	0.1	0.1	5.0											
		Manure excreted indoor	0.3	1.5	0.4	1.7	1.1	0.5	0.7	2.4	0.7	0.2	0.0	9.6											
		Total amount of livestock manure	0.8	3.6	0.6	3.1	2.2	1.0	1.9	4.6	0.9	0.3	0.3	19.4											
	GHG costs - Manure	Manure from intensive systems	-22.1	-34.3	-101.3	-97.3	-41.5	-58.6	-37.5	-24.1	-109.2	-85.8	-28.3	-50.1											
		Manure excreted indoor	-39.0	-35.4	-56.3	-75.4	-39.8	-48.5	-90.7	-36.6	-114.9	-78.3	-131.9	-56.1											
Total amount of livestock manure		-45.4	-45.9	-55.8	-68.9	-48.1	-53.3	-75.9	-48.6	-98.7	-73.7	-65.2	-57.4												
TSS (2050)	Potentials - Energy crops	No grazing intensification	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	4.3	2.0	0.0	0.0	3.7	0.4	10.8											
		Grazing intensification on highly productive sites	0.0	0.0	4.1	1.7	0.0	9.4	6.6	21.2	0.4	7.0	2.4	52.9											
		Universal grazing intensification	0.0	0.0	5.5	6.3	0.0	11.3	10.1	35.6	4.3	8.2	4.0	85.3											
	GHG costs - Energy crops	No grazing intensification				30.8			19.8	24.9			27.7	20.3	23.8										
		Direct GHG costs only (opportunity GHG costs excluded)				-12.2			-7.6	-10.9			-8.0	-5.7	-8.4										
		Grazing intensification on highly productive sites				96.2	317.6		25.0	46.0	32.1	238.9	18.5	60.1	66.3										
		Sensitivity analysis: Regrowth on highly prod.sites				28.4	40.3		19.4	22.5	21.1	32.3	27.7	21.7	23.1										
		Direct GHG costs only (opportunity GHG costs excluded)				-1.5	-0.7		-3.7	-3.8	-0.4	-0.3	-4.4	-1.6	-2.1										
		Universal grazing intensification				96.0	114.4		22.4	35.7	21.5	24.1	16.6	43.4	49.0										
	GHG costs - Energy crops	Sensitivity analysis: Regrowth on highly prod.sites				28.4	40.3		19.3	22.1	21.1	32.3	27.7	21.8	24.1										
		Direct GHG costs only (opportunity GHG costs excluded)				1.7	-0.1		-3.0	-2.2	-0.2	-1.1	-3.8	-0.1	-0.9										
	Potentials - Crop residues	40% residue removal rate	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.6	0.1	0.2	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.2	0.1	3.3											
		60% residue removal rate	0.7	3.3	1.2	3.3	3.0	1.6	2.1	2.6	1.4	0.8	0.3	20.4											
	GHG costs - Crop residues	40% residue removal rate	12.8	53.3	31.8	17.5	23.2	12.1	18.1	12.5	22.5	24.3	11.0	21.0											
		60% residue removal rate	13.0	25.2	26.7	18.3	13.2	13.1	18.7	13.2	22.1	22.2	11.0	18.3											
	Potentials: Manure	Manure from intensive systems	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.7	0.1	0.1	1.2	1.5	0.3	0.0	0.1	4.3											
		Manure excreted indoor	0.2	1.5	0.3	1.4	1.2	0.5	0.6	2.2	0.5	0.2	0.0	8.6											
		Total amount of livestock manure	0.7	3.5	0.6	2.5	2.2	1.0	1.5	4.1	0.8	0.2	0.2	17.4											
	GHG costs - Manure	Manure from intensive systems	-22.2	-34.1	-101.3	-98.6	-40.8	-58.9	-37.5	-24.4	-108.7	-85.8	-28.3	-49.7											
		Manure excreted indoor	-39.2	-35.3	-56.3	-76.3	-39.2	-48.7	-90.7	-37.0	-114.3	-78.3	-131.9	-54.7											
Total amount of livestock manure		-45.5	-45.9	-55.8	-69.5	-47.7	-53.4	-75.9	-48.9	-98.3	-73.7	-65.2	-56.6												
SSS (2050)	Potentials - Energy crops	No grazing intensification	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	3.1	2.2	0.0	0.0	3.7	0.5	9.9											
		Grazing intensification on highly productive sites	0.0	0.0	3.3	1.2	0.0	7.2	6.0	16.5	0.3	6.4	2.1	43.0											
		Universal grazing intensification	0.0	0.0	4.5	4.6	0.0	8.7	8.8	28.0	3.6	7.4	3.4	69.0											
	GHG costs - Energy crops	No grazing intensification				30.8			19.8	24.9			27.7	20.3	24.3										
		Direct GHG costs only (opportunity GHG costs excluded)				-12.2			-7.6	-10.9			-8.0	-5.7	-8.5										
		Grazing intensification on highly productive sites				83.3	303.1		23.0	39.1	28.5	199.3	19.0	50.0	58.0										
		Sensitivity analysis: Regrowth on highly prod.sites				28.4	40.3		19.4	22.7	21.1	32.3	27.7	21.5	23.2										
		Direct GHG costs only (opportunity GHG costs excluded)				-1.7	-0.7		-3.5	-4.5	-0.4	-0.3	-4.8	-2.0	-2.3										
		Universal grazing intensification				108.9	144.1		21.1	36.1	20.5	24.0	18.0	42.9	50.8										
	GHG costs - Energy crops	Sensitivity analysis: Regrowth on highly prod.sites				28.4	40.3		19.3	22.3	21.1	32.3	27.7	21.7	24.1										
		Direct GHG costs only (opportunity GHG costs excluded)				1.5	0.1		-2.8	-2.8	-0.2	-1.1	-4.3	-0.5	-1.0										
	Potentials - Crop residues	40% residue removal rate	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.7	0.1	0.2	0.6	0.3	0.6	0.3	0.1	3.5											
		60% residue removal rate	0.8	3.2	1.3	3.7	3.0	1.7	2.4	2.7	1.6	0.9	0.4	21.5											
	GHG costs - Crop residues	40% residue removal rate	12.5	54.9	30.1	16.9	22.5	12.1	16.4	12.5	19.8	21.9	9.8	19.7											
		60% residue removal rate	12.8	25.7	25.5	17.6	13.0	13.0	16.6	13.2	19.8	20.2	9.8	17.6											
	Potentials: Manure	Manure from intensive systems	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.9	0.1	0.1	1.6	1.6	0.4	0.1	0.2	5.2											
		Manure excreted indoor	0.3	1.3	0.4	1.8	1.2	0.5	0.8	2.4	0.7	0.2	0.0	9.6											
		Total amount of livestock manure	0.8	3.1	0.6	3.2	2.3	1.0	2.0	4.6	1.0	0.3	0.3	19.3											
	GHG costs - Manure	Manure from intensive systems	-22.0	-34.5	-101.3	-97.6	-40.7	-59.2	-37.5	-24.3	-111.7	-85.8	-28.3	-50.7											
		Manure excreted indoor	-38.9	-35.6	-56.3	-75.6	-39.2	-48.9	-90.7	-36.8	-117.8	-78.3	-131.9	-57.2											
Total amount of livestock manure		-45.3	-46.0	-55.8	-69.0	-47.7	-53.5	-75.9	-48.7	-100.9	-73.7	-65.2	-58.1												
BAU with healthy ref.diet (2050)	Potentials - Energy crops	No grazing intensification	0.0	0.0	3.9	3.6	0.0	10.1	9.6	10.7	3.7	7.3	2.2	51.1											
		Grazing intensification on highly productive sites	0.0	1.6	7.8	5.6	0.0	15.3	14.4	34.1	4.1	10.7	4.2	97.9											
		Universal grazing intensification	0.0	2.1	9.0	11.0	0.0	16.9	17.6	48.3	8.4	11.7	5.7	130.6											
	GHG costs - Energy crops	No grazing intensification				30.8	46.9		19.8	24.9	20.2	29.8	27.7	20.3	25.5										
		Direct GHG costs only (opportunity GHG costs excluded)				-12.2	-12.8		-7.6	-10.9	-7.0	-9.0	-8.0	-5.7	-8.9										
		Grazing intensification on highly productive sites				638.5	72.2	136.6		24.2	37.0	29.1	51.1	21.9	47.0	51.1									
		Sensitivity analysis: Regrowth on highly prod.sites				15.9	29.5	44.5		19.5	23.7	20.8	30.1	27.7	21.1	24.2									
		Direct GHG costs only (opportunity GHG costs excluded)				-0.3	-6.4	-8.4		-5.1	-7.5	-2.4	-8.1	-5.6	-3.4	-4.9									
		Universal grazing intensification				535.2	73.1	80.3		22.7	32.5	21.8	26.1	20.3	38.6	41.8									
	GHG costs - Energy crops	Sensitivity analysis: Regrowth on highly prod.sites				15.9	29.3	42.5		19.5	23.3	20.9	31.2	27.7	21.3	24.6									
		Direct GHG costs only (opportunity GHG costs excluded																							

4.3.2 Agricultural land use 2050

The following tables summarize agricultural land use in 2050 for the scenarios BAU, TSS and SSS for the different grazing intensification levels and the cases “Bioenergy” and “Regrowth”. Note that the scenarios are based on the respective FAO scenarios (FAO, 2018) with regard to crop yields and diets, but land-use data are derived from own calculations and representations of land types that are partly different from those used by FAO (see explanations in section 2 of the main article and section 3.1 in this document).

Table S12. Agricultural land use in 2050 in the scenario BAU

Agricultural land use in 2050 (Mha)		Northern Africa and Western Asia	Sub-Saharan Africa	Central Asia and Russian Federation	Eastern Asia	Southern Asia	South-east Asia	Northern America	Latin America & the Caribbean	Western Europe	Eastern & South-eastern Europe	Oceania and Australia	World
Bioenergy case													
No grazing intensification	Cropland excl. energy crops	58.7	466.0	70.4	201.1	274.5	93.7	96.4	151.7	57.0	35.8	18.1	1523.2
	Grazing land class1	0.0	0.0	77.1	108.2	0.0	40.6	112.9	283.8	51.8	45.5	46.6	766.5
	Grazing land class2	1.4	209.6	48.6	36.0	6.6	36.2	57.3	179.8	19.9	5.0	37.4	638.0
	Grazing land class3	21.0	136.2	111.5	146.2	30.6	4.7	54.4	50.2	14.4	5.1	92.7	667.1
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Cropland used for energy crops	0.0	0.0	10.7	0.0	0.0	24.9	32.1	2.9	1.9	29.8	7.9	110.2
Grazing intensification on highly productive sites	Cropland excl. energy crops	58.7	466.0	70.4	201.1	274.5	93.7	96.4	151.7	57.0	35.8	18.1	1523.2
	Grazing land class1	0.0	0.0	48.5	93.8	0.0	25.6	80.3	198.3	49.5	28.6	33.5	558.1
	Grazing land class2	1.4	209.6	48.6	36.0	6.6	36.2	57.3	179.8	19.9	5.0	37.4	638.0
	Grazing land class3	21.0	136.2	111.5	146.2	30.6	4.7	54.4	50.2	14.4	5.1	92.7	667.1
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Cropland used for energy crops	0.0	0.0	39.3	14.4	0.0	39.9	64.7	88.4	4.2	46.7	21.0	318.6
Universal grazing intensification	Cropland excl. energy crops	58.7	466.0	70.4	201.1	274.5	93.7	96.4	151.7	57.0	35.8	18.1	1523.2
	Grazing land class1	0.0	0.0	39.1	54.9	0.0	20.6	57.3	143.9	26.3	23.1	23.7	388.8
	Grazing land class2	1.4	209.6	48.6	36.0	6.6	36.2	57.3	179.8	19.9	5.0	37.4	638.0
	Grazing land class3	21.0	136.2	111.5	146.2	30.6	4.7	54.4	50.2	14.4	5.1	92.7	667.1
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Cropland used for energy crops	0.0	0.0	48.7	53.3	0.0	44.9	87.7	142.8	27.4	52.2	30.8	487.9
Regrowth case													
No grazing intensification	Cropland	58.7	466.0	70.4	201.1	274.5	93.7	96.4	151.7	57.0	35.8	18.1	1523.2
	Grazing land class1	0.0	0.0	77.1	108.2	0.0	40.6	112.9	283.8	51.8	45.5	46.6	766.5
	Grazing land class2	1.4	209.6	48.6	36.0	6.6	36.2	57.3	179.8	19.9	5.0	37.4	638.0
	Grazing land class3	21.0	136.2	111.5	146.2	30.6	4.7	54.4	50.2	14.4	5.1	92.7	667.1
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Regrowth areas (highly prod.)	0.0	0.0	10.7	0.0	0.0	24.9	32.1	2.9	1.9	29.8	7.9	110.2
Regrowth areas (med.-low prod.)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
Grazing intensification on highly productive sites	Cropland	58.7	466.0	70.4	201.1	274.5	93.7	96.4	151.7	57.0	35.8	18.1	1523.2
	Grazing land class1	0.0	0.0	77.1	108.2	0.0	40.6	112.9	283.8	51.8	45.5	46.6	766.5
	Grazing land class2	0.6	86.6	20.1	14.9	2.7	15.0	23.6	74.3	8.2	2.1	15.4	263.5
	Grazing land class3	8.7	56.2	46.0	60.4	12.7	1.9	22.5	20.7	6.0	2.1	38.3	275.5
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Regrowth areas (highly prod.)	0.0	0.0	10.7	0.0	0.0	24.9	32.1	2.9	1.9	29.8	7.9	110.2
Regrowth areas (med.-low prod.)	13.2	203.0	94.0	107.0	21.9	24.0	65.6	135.1	20.2	5.9	76.4	766.1	
Universal grazing intensification	Cropland	58.7	466.0	70.4	201.1	274.5	93.7	96.4	151.7	57.0	35.8	18.1	1523.2
	Grazing land class1	0.0	0.0	77.1	108.2	0.0	40.6	112.9	283.8	51.8	45.5	46.6	766.5
	Grazing land class2	0.5	74.8	17.3	12.9	2.4	12.9	20.4	64.1	7.1	1.8	13.3	227.5
	Grazing land class3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Regrowth areas (highly prod.)	0.0	0.0	10.7	0.0	0.0	24.9	32.1	2.9	1.9	29.8	7.9	110.2
Regrowth areas (med.-low prod.)	22.0	271.1	142.8	169.4	34.9	28.0	91.3	165.9	27.3	8.3	116.8	1077.6	

Table S13. Agricultural land use in 2050 in the Towards sustainability (TSS) scenario

Agricultural land use in 2050 (Mha)		Northern Africa and Western Asia	Sub-Saharan Africa	Central Asia and Russian Federation	Eastern Asia	Southern Asia	South-east Asia	Northern America	Latin America & the Caribbean	Western Europe	Eastern & South-eastern Europe	Oceania and Australia	World
Bioenergy case													
No grazing intensification	Cropland excl. energy crops	58.7	466.0	78.4	204.8	274.5	103.5	112.1	175.1	64.4	43.7	22.7	1603.8
	Grazing land class1	0.0	0.0	77.1	104.5	0.0	40.6	112.9	263.4	46.2	45.5	46.6	736.8
	Grazing land class2	1.4	209.6	48.6	36.0	6.6	36.2	57.3	179.8	19.9	5.0	37.4	638.0
	Grazing land class3	21.0	136.2	111.5	146.2	30.6	4.7	54.4	50.2	14.4	5.1	92.7	667.1
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
Grazing intensification on highly productive sites	Cropland used for energy crops	0.0	0.0	2.8	0.0	0.0	15.0	16.4	0.0	0.0	21.9	3.3	59.3
	Cropland excl. energy crops	58.7	466.0	78.4	204.8	274.5	103.5	112.1	175.1	64.4	43.7	22.7	1603.8
	Grazing land class1	0.0	0.0	43.8	88.3	0.0	23.1	75.0	171.0	43.9	25.9	31.4	502.2
	Grazing land class2	1.4	209.6	48.6	36.0	6.6	36.2	57.3	179.8	19.9	5.0	37.4	638.0
	Grazing land class3	21.0	136.2	111.5	146.2	30.6	4.7	54.4	50.2	14.4	5.1	92.7	667.1
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
Universal grazing intensification	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Cropland used for energy crops	0.0	0.0	36.1	16.2	0.0	32.5	54.3	92.4	2.4	41.5	18.5	299.9
	Cropland excl. energy crops	58.7	466.0	78.4	204.8	274.5	103.5	112.1	175.1	64.4	43.7	22.7	1603.8
	Grazing land class1	0.0	0.0	31.7	43.0	0.0	16.7	46.4	108.3	19.0	18.7	19.2	303.1
	Grazing land class2	1.4	209.6	48.6	36.0	6.6	36.2	57.3	179.8	19.9	5.0	37.4	638.0
	Grazing land class3	21.0	136.2	111.5	146.2	30.6	4.7	54.4	50.2	14.4	5.1	92.7	667.1
Regrowth case	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Regrowth areas (highly prod.)	0.0	0.0	2.8	0.0	0.0	15.0	16.4	0.0	0.0	21.9	3.3	59.3
	Regrowth areas (med.-low prod.)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Cropland	58.7	466.0	78.4	204.8	274.5	103.5	112.1	175.1	64.4	43.7	22.7	1603.8
	Grazing intensification on highly productive sites	Grazing land class1	0.0	0.0	77.1	104.5	0.0	40.6	112.9	263.4	46.2	45.5	46.6
Grazing land class2		0.4	60.2	14.0	10.3	1.9	10.4	16.4	51.6	5.7	1.4	10.7	183.2
Grazing land class3		6.0	39.1	32.0	42.0	8.8	1.3	15.6	14.4	4.1	1.5	26.6	191.5
Grazing land class4		124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
Non-productive land		6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
Regrowth areas (highly prod.)		0.0	0.0	2.8	0.0	0.0	15.0	16.4	0.0	0.0	21.9	3.3	59.3
Universal grazing intensification	Regrowth areas (med.-low prod.)	16.0	246.5	114.1	129.9	26.6	29.1	79.6	164.0	24.5	7.2	92.7	930.4
	Cropland	58.7	466.0	78.4	204.8	274.5	103.5	112.1	175.1	64.4	43.7	22.7	1603.8
	Grazing land class1	0.0	0.0	77.1	104.5	0.0	40.6	112.9	263.4	46.2	45.5	46.6	736.8
	Grazing land class2	0.3	47.6	11.0	8.2	1.5	8.2	13.0	40.8	4.5	1.1	8.5	144.8
	Grazing land class3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
Universal grazing intensification	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Regrowth areas (highly prod.)	0.0	0.0	2.8	0.0	0.0	15.0	16.4	0.0	0.0	21.9	3.3	59.3
	Regrowth areas (med.-low prod.)	22.1	298.2	149.1	174.0	35.7	32.7	98.7	189.2	29.9	9.0	121.6	1160.3

Table S14. Agricultural land use in 2050 in the Stratified societies (SSS) scenario

		Northern Africa and Western Asia	Sub-Saharan Africa	Central Asia and Russian Federation	Eastern Asia	Southern Asia	South-east Asia	Northern America	Latin America & the Caribbean	Western Europe	Eastern & South-eastern Europe	Oceania and Australia	World
Agricultural land use in 2050 (Mha)													
Bioenergy case													
No grazing intensification	Cropland excl. energy crops	58.7	466.0	78.5	214.1	274.5	107.7	110.1	181.4	62.4	43.7	22.0	1619.0
	Grazing land class1	0.0	0.0	77.1	95.2	0.0	40.6	112.9	257.0	48.3	45.5	46.6	723.3
	Grazing land class2	1.4	209.6	48.6	36.0	6.6	36.2	57.3	179.8	19.9	5.0	37.4	638.0
	Grazing land class3	21.0	136.2	111.5	146.2	30.6	4.7	54.4	50.2	14.4	5.1	92.7	667.1
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Cropland used for energy crops	0.0	0.0	2.6	0.0	0.0	10.8	18.3	0.0	0.0	21.9	4.0	57.6
Grazing intensification on highly productive sites	Cropland excl. energy crops	58.7	466.0	78.5	214.1	274.5	107.7	110.1	181.4	62.4	43.7	22.0	1619.0
	Grazing land class1	0.0	0.0	50.5	83.5	0.0	26.6	82.6	185.1	46.3	29.8	34.4	538.9
	Grazing land class2	1.4	209.6	48.6	36.0	6.6	36.2	57.3	179.8	19.9	5.0	37.4	638.0
	Grazing land class3	21.0	136.2	111.5	146.2	30.6	4.7	54.4	50.2	14.4	5.1	92.7	667.1
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Cropland used for energy crops	0.0	0.0	29.2	11.8	0.0	24.8	48.6	71.9	2.0	37.5	16.2	241.9
Universal grazing intensification	Cropland excl. energy crops	58.7	466.0	78.5	214.1	274.5	107.7	110.1	181.4	62.4	43.7	22.0	1619.0
	Grazing land class1	0.0	0.0	40.5	50.1	0.0	21.3	59.3	135.1	25.4	23.9	24.5	380.1
	Grazing land class2	1.4	209.6	48.6	36.0	6.6	36.2	57.3	179.8	19.9	5.0	37.4	638.0
	Grazing land class3	21.0	136.2	111.5	146.2	30.6	4.7	54.4	50.2	14.4	5.1	92.7	667.1
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Cropland used for energy crops	0.0	0.0	39.2	45.2	0.0	30.1	71.9	121.9	22.9	43.5	26.1	400.7
Regrowth case													
No grazing intensification	Cropland	58.7	466.0	78.5	214.1	274.5	107.7	110.1	181.4	62.4	43.7	22.0	1619.0
	Grazing land class1	0.0	0.0	77.1	95.2	0.0	40.6	112.9	257.0	48.3	45.5	46.6	723.3
	Grazing land class2	1.4	209.6	48.6	36.0	6.6	36.2	57.3	179.8	19.9	5.0	37.4	638.0
	Grazing land class3	21.0	136.2	111.5	146.2	30.6	4.7	54.4	50.2	14.4	5.1	92.7	667.1
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Regrowth areas (highly prod.)	0.0	0.0	2.6	0.0	0.0	10.8	18.3	0.0	0.0	21.9	4.0	57.6
Regrowth areas (med.-low prod.)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
Grazing intensification on highly productive sites	Cropland	58.7	466.0	78.5	214.1	274.5	107.7	110.1	181.4	62.4	43.7	22.0	1619.0
	Grazing land class1	0.0	0.0	77.1	95.2	0.0	40.6	112.9	257.0	48.3	45.5	46.6	723.3
	Grazing land class2	0.7	106.2	24.6	18.3	3.3	18.3	29.0	91.1	10.1	2.5	18.9	323.2
	Grazing land class3	10.7	69.0	56.5	74.0	15.5	2.4	27.6	25.4	7.3	2.6	47.0	337.9
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Regrowth areas (highly prod.)	0.0	0.0	2.6	0.0	0.0	10.8	18.3	0.0	0.0	21.9	4.0	57.6
Regrowth areas (med.-low prod.)	11.1	170.6	79.0	89.9	18.4	20.2	55.1	113.5	17.0	5.0	64.2	643.9	
Universal grazing intensification	Cropland	58.7	466.0	78.5	214.1	274.5	107.7	110.1	181.4	62.4	43.7	22.0	1619.0
	Grazing land class1	0.0	0.0	77.1	95.2	0.0	40.6	112.9	257.0	48.3	45.5	46.6	723.3
	Grazing land class2	0.6	95.0	22.1	16.3	3.0	16.4	26.0	81.5	9.0	2.3	16.9	289.2
	Grazing land class3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Regrowth areas (highly prod.)	0.0	0.0	2.6	0.0	0.0	10.8	18.3	0.0	0.0	21.9	4.0	57.6
Regrowth areas (med.-low prod.)	21.8	250.8	138.1	165.9	34.2	24.5	85.7	148.5	25.3	7.8	113.1	1015.9	

Table S15. Agricultural land use in 2050 in the scenario BAU with healthy reference diet

Agricultural land use in 2050 (Mha)		Northern Africa and Western Asia	Sub-Saharan Africa	Central Asia and Russian Federation	Eastern Asia	Southern Asia	South-east Asia	Northern America	Latin America & the Caribbean	Western Europe	Eastern & South-eastern Europe	Oceania and Australia	World
Bioenergy case													
No grazing intensification	Cropland excl. energy crops	58.7	443.3	47.4	149.1	274.5	83.6	50.1	108.1	35.0	22.4	8.7	1280.9
	Grazing land class1	0.0	22.6	77.1	125.3	0.0	40.6	112.9	283.8	51.8	45.5	46.6	806.2
	Grazing land class2	1.4	209.6	48.6	36.0	6.6	36.2	57.3	179.8	19.9	5.0	37.4	638.0
	Grazing land class3	21.0	136.2	111.5	146.2	30.6	4.7	54.4	50.2	14.4	5.1	92.7	667.1
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Cropland used for energy crops	0.0	0.0	33.7	34.9	0.0	34.9	78.4	46.6	23.8	43.2	17.2	312.8
Grazing intensification on highly productive sites	Cropland excl. energy crops	58.7	443.3	47.4	149.1	274.5	83.6	50.1	108.1	35.0	22.4	8.7	1280.9
	Grazing land class1	0.0	12.6	43.0	105.4	0.0	22.7	74.0	181.8	49.0	25.4	31.0	545.0
	Grazing land class2	1.4	209.6	48.6	36.0	6.6	36.2	57.3	179.8	19.9	5.0	37.4	638.0
	Grazing land class3	21.0	136.2	111.5	146.2	30.6	4.7	54.4	50.2	14.4	5.1	92.7	667.1
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Cropland used for energy crops	0.0	10.0	67.8	54.8	0.0	52.9	117.2	148.5	26.6	63.3	32.9	574.0
Universal grazing intensification	Cropland excl. energy crops	58.7	443.3	47.4	149.1	274.5	83.6	50.1	108.1	35.0	22.4	8.7	1280.9
	Grazing land class1	0.0	9.6	32.7	53.1	0.0	17.2	47.8	120.3	21.9	19.3	19.8	341.7
	Grazing land class2	1.4	209.6	48.6	36.0	6.6	36.2	57.3	179.8	19.9	5.0	37.4	638.0
	Grazing land class3	21.0	136.2	111.5	146.2	30.6	4.7	54.4	50.2	14.4	5.1	92.7	667.1
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Cropland used for energy crops	0.0	13.0	78.1	107.1	0.0	58.3	143.5	210.1	53.7	69.4	44.1	777.3
Regrowth case													
No grazing intensification	Cropland	58.7	443.3	47.4	149.1	274.5	83.6	50.1	108.1	35.0	22.4	8.7	1280.9
	Grazing land class1	0.0	22.6	77.1	125.3	0.0	40.6	112.9	283.8	51.8	45.5	46.6	806.2
	Grazing land class2	1.4	209.6	48.6	36.0	6.6	36.2	57.3	179.8	19.9	5.0	37.4	638.0
	Grazing land class3	21.0	136.2	111.5	146.2	30.6	4.7	54.4	50.2	14.4	5.1	92.7	667.1
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Regrowth areas (highly prod.)	0.0	0.0	33.7	34.9	0.0	34.9	78.4	46.6	23.8	43.2	17.2	312.8
Regrowth areas (med.-low prod.)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
Grazing intensification on highly productive sites	Cropland	58.7	443.3	47.4	149.1	274.5	83.6	50.1	108.1	35.0	22.4	8.7	1280.9
	Grazing land class1	0.0	22.6	77.1	125.3	0.0	40.6	112.9	283.8	51.8	45.5	46.6	806.2
	Grazing land class2	0.3	39.6	9.2	6.8	1.2	6.8	10.8	33.9	3.8	0.9	7.1	120.4
	Grazing land class3	4.0	25.7	21.0	27.6	5.8	0.9	10.3	9.5	2.7	1.0	17.5	125.9
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Regrowth areas (highly prod.)	0.0	0.0	33.7	34.9	0.0	34.9	78.4	46.6	23.8	43.2	17.2	312.8
Regrowth areas (med.-low prod.)	18.2	280.6	129.9	147.8	30.2	33.2	90.6	186.6	27.9	8.2	105.5	1058.7	
Universal grazing intensification	Cropland	58.7	443.3	47.4	149.1	274.5	83.6	50.1	108.1	35.0	22.4	8.7	1280.9
	Grazing land class1	0.0	22.6	77.1	125.3	0.0	40.6	112.9	283.8	51.8	45.5	46.6	806.2
	Grazing land class2	0.2	30.8	7.1	5.3	1.0	5.3	8.4	26.4	2.9	0.7	5.5	93.7
	Grazing land class3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grazing land class4	124.4	363.3	266.0	145.6	73.5	19.5	175.2	270.7	19.7	1.3	184.6	1643.8
	Non-productive land	6.2	20.7	25.6	15.9	19.5	5.7	41.3	8.5	21.8	7.0	3.3	175.4
	Regrowth areas (highly prod.)	0.0	0.0	33.7	34.9	0.0	34.9	78.4	46.6	23.8	43.2	17.2	312.8
Regrowth areas (med.-low prod.)	22.3	315.0	153.0	176.9	36.3	35.6	103.3	203.6	31.5	9.4	124.6	1211.4	

4.3.3 CO₂ emissions resulting from land-use change

Table S16. CO₂ emissions from C stock changes due to land-use change in the scenario BAU (annual average emissions during 2012 to 2050 in Mt CO₂e/yr)

Annual average CO ₂ emissions from C stock changes (Mt CO ₂ e/yr)		Northern Africa and Western Asia	Sub-Saharan Africa	Central Asia and Russian Federation	Eastern Asia	Southern Asia	South-east Asia	Northern America	Latin America & the Caribbean	Western Europe	Eastern & South-eastern Europe	Oceania and Australia	World
Bioenergy case													
No grazing intensification	Cropland: annual crops -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	-15.0	0.0	0.0	-54.6	-42.9	-4.7	-2.7	-40.4	-5.8	-166.1
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	274.9	0.0	5.7	4.1	4.8	2.8	0.8	0.5	1.3	0.3	297.7
	Grassland -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.2	16.5	25.0	14.6	0.0	2.7	16.1	22.1	2.6	2.9	7.6	110.4
Total	2.7	291.4	10.0	20.3	4.1	-47.0	-24.0	18.2	0.4	-36.2	2.1	242.0	
Grazing intensification on highly productive sites	Cropland: annual crops -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	-15.0	0.0	0.0	-54.6	-42.9	-4.7	-2.7	-40.4	-5.8	-166.1
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	274.9	0.0	5.7	4.1	4.8	2.8	0.8	0.5	1.3	0.3	297.7
	Grassland -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	-4.8	-3.5	0.0	-2.5	-6.4	-13.4	-0.7	-2.6	-2.3	-36.1
	Grassland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.2	16.5	27.7	17.1	0.0	3.5	19.7	28.3	3.2	4.6	8.7	129.5
Total	2.7	291.4	7.9	19.3	4.1	-48.8	-26.7	11.0	0.3	-37.1	0.9	225.0	
Universal grazing intensification	Cropland: annual crops -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	-15.0	0.0	0.0	-54.6	-42.9	-4.7	-2.7	-40.4	-5.8	-166.1
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	274.9	0.0	5.7	4.1	4.8	2.8	0.8	0.5	1.3	0.3	297.7
	Grassland -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	-6.3	-12.8	0.0	-3.4	-11.0	-21.9	-7.6	-3.4	-4.0	-70.4
	Grassland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.5	30.8	43.2	26.9	0.0	5.1	27.4	36.0	5.7	4.8	13.4	193.7
Total	3.0	305.7	21.8	19.8	4.1	-48.0	-23.7	10.2	-4.1	-37.8	3.8	254.9	
Regrowth case													
No grazing intensification	Cropland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	-52.9	0.0	0.0	-197.3	-140.7	-18.4	-11.5	-180.1	-26.4	-627.2
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	274.9	0.0	5.7	4.1	4.8	2.8	0.8	0.5	1.3	0.3	297.7
	Grassland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.2	16.5	25.0	14.6	0.0	2.7	16.1	22.1	2.6	2.9	7.6	110.4
	Total	2.7	291.4	-27.9	20.3	4.1	-189.7	-121.8	4.6	-8.5	-175.9	-18.5	-219.1
Grazing intensification on highly prod. sites	Cropland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	-52.9	0.0	0.0	-197.3	-140.7	-18.4	-11.5	-180.1	-26.4	-627.2
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	274.9	0.0	5.7	4.1	4.8	2.8	0.8	0.5	1.3	0.3	297.7
	Grassland -> Vegetation regrowth	-31.5	-735.0	-323.8	-436.5	-47.9	-126.1	-217.2	-575.6	-73.1	-27.2	-113.0	-2706.9
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.1	11.7	25.8	13.8	0.0	3.9	19.5	30.0	2.2	6.7	7.8	121.4
	Total C stock changes	-28.9	-448.4	-350.9	-417.0	-43.9	-314.6	-335.6	-563.2	-82.0	-199.3	-131.4	-2915.0
Universal grazing intensification	Cropland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	-52.9	0.0	0.0	-197.3	-140.7	-18.4	-11.5	-180.1	-26.4	-627.2
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	274.9	0.0	5.7	4.1	4.8	2.8	0.8	0.5	1.3	0.3	297.7
	Grassland -> Vegetation regrowth	-51.7	-869.6	-486.2	-682.6	-74.0	-143.8	-288.3	-674.7	-97.0	-37.5	-145.2	-3550.8
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.0	13.7	24.6	12.2	0.0	4.5	20.5	32.5	2.3	6.8	7.6	124.5
	Total C stock changes	-49.2	-581.1	-514.6	-664.7	-70.0	-331.8	-405.7	-659.8	-105.7	-209.5	-163.7	-3755.7

Table S17. CO₂ emissions from C stock changes due to land-use change in the Towards sustainability (TSS) scenario (annual average emissions during 2012 to 2050 in Mt CO₂e/yr)

Annual average CO ₂ emissions from C stock changes (Mt CO ₂ e/yr)		Northern Africa and Western Asia	Sub-Saharan Africa	Central Asia and Russian Federation	Eastern Asia	Southern Asia	South-east Asia	Northern America	Latin America & the Caribbean	Western Europe	Eastern & South-eastern Europe	Oceania and Australia	World
Bioenergy case													
No grazing intensification	Cropland: annual crops -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	-3.9	0.0	0.0	-33.0	-21.9	0.0	0.0	-29.7	-2.4	-90.8
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	274.9	0.0	6.9	4.1	4.8	2.8	24.1	3.7	1.3	0.3	325.4
	Grassland -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.1	11.8	17.9	10.4	0.0	2.0	11.5	15.5	1.8	2.1	5.5	78.6
Total	2.7	286.7	14.0	17.3	4.1	-26.2	-7.6	39.5	5.5	-26.3	3.4	313.1	
Grazing intensification on highly productive sites	Cropland: annual crops -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	-3.9	0.0	0.0	-33.0	-21.9	0.0	0.0	-29.7	-2.4	-90.8
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	274.9	0.0	6.9	4.1	4.8	2.8	24.1	3.7	1.3	0.3	325.4
	Grassland -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	-5.6	-3.9	0.0	-2.9	-7.5	-14.5	-0.7	-3.0	-2.7	-40.7
	Grassland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.1	11.8	21.0	13.2	0.0	2.9	15.8	22.1	2.4	4.1	6.7	100.1
Total	2.7	286.7	11.6	16.2	4.1	-28.2	-10.8	31.7	5.4	-27.3	1.9	293.9	
Universal grazing intensification	Cropland: annual crops -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	-3.9	0.0	0.0	-33.0	-21.9	0.0	0.0	-29.7	-2.4	-90.8
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	274.9	0.0	6.9	4.1	4.8	2.8	24.1	3.7	1.3	0.3	325.4
	Grassland -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	-7.6	-14.8	0.0	-4.0	-13.1	-24.3	-8.1	-4.1	-4.8	-80.8
	Grassland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.5	28.4	38.9	24.7	0.0	4.7	24.5	31.2	5.4	4.2	12.1	174.5
Total	3.0	303.3	27.4	16.8	4.1	-27.4	-7.7	31.0	0.9	-28.3	5.2	328.3	
Regrowth case													
No grazing intensification	Cropland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	-13.7	0.0	0.0	-119.1	-71.8	0.0	0.0	-132.2	-10.9	-347.7
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	274.9	0.0	6.9	4.1	4.8	2.8	24.1	3.7	1.3	0.3	325.4
	Grassland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.1	11.8	17.9	10.4	0.0	2.0	11.5	15.5	1.8	2.1	5.5	78.6
	Total	2.7	286.7	4.2	17.3	4.1	-112.3	-57.5	39.5	5.5	-128.8	-5.2	56.2
Grazing intensification on highly productive sites	Cropland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	-13.7	0.0	0.0	-119.1	-71.8	0.0	0.0	-132.2	-10.9	-347.7
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	274.9	0.0	6.9	4.1	4.8	2.8	24.1	3.7	1.3	0.3	325.4
	Grassland -> Vegetation regrowth	-38.3	-892.5	-393.2	-530.1	-58.2	-153.1	-263.8	-699.1	-88.8	-33.0	-137.2	-3287.3
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.0	7.6	20.5	10.5	0.0	3.6	16.4	24.8	1.6	6.6	6.1	97.7
	Total C stock changes	-35.7	-610.0	-386.4	-512.7	-54.1	-263.8	-316.4	-650.2	-83.5	-157.4	-141.7	-3212.0
Universal grazing intensification	Cropland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	-13.7	0.0	0.0	-119.1	-71.8	0.0	0.0	-132.2	-10.9	-347.7
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	274.9	0.0	6.9	4.1	4.8	2.8	24.1	3.7	1.3	0.3	325.4
	Grassland -> Vegetation regrowth	-52.4	-1008.6	-510.0	-704.8	-76.8	-169.6	-318.0	-785.9	-107.0	-40.7	-162.4	-3936.1
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.0	9.4	20.2	9.8	0.0	4.0	17.4	26.8	1.8	6.6	6.2	102.2
	Total C stock changes	-49.9	-724.3	-503.4	-688.0	-72.7	-279.9	-369.6	-735.0	-101.6	-165.0	-166.8	-3856.2

Table S18. CO₂ emissions from C stock changes due to land-use change in the Stratified societies (SSS) scenario (annual average emissions during 2012 to 2050 in Mt CO₂e/yr)

Annual average CO ₂ emissions from C stock changes (Mt CO ₂ e/yr)		Northern Africa and Western Asia	Sub-Saharan Africa	Central Asia and Russian Federation	Eastern Asia	Southern Asia	South-east Asia	Northern America	Latin America & the Caribbean	Western Europe	Eastern & South-eastern Europe	Oceania and Australia	World
Bioenergy case													
No grazing intensification	Cropland: annual crops -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	-3.6	0.0	0.0	-23.7	-24.5	0.0	0.0	-29.7	-2.9	-84.4
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	274.9	0.0	9.9	4.1	4.8	2.8	31.3	2.5	1.3	0.3	334.3
	Grassland -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.2	18.6	28.1	16.1	0.0	3.1	18.1	24.1	2.9	3.3	8.6	123.0
Total	2.8	293.5	24.5	26.0	4.1	-15.8	-3.6	55.4	5.4	-25.1	5.9	372.9	
Grazing intensification on highly productive sites	Cropland: annual crops -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	-3.6	0.0	0.0	-23.7	-24.5	0.0	0.0	-29.7	-2.9	-84.4
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	274.9	0.0	9.9	4.1	4.8	2.8	31.3	2.5	1.3	0.3	334.3
	Grassland -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	-4.4	-2.8	0.0	-2.3	-6.0	-11.3	-0.6	-2.4	-2.1	-32.0
	Grassland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.2	18.6	30.6	18.2	0.0	3.8	21.5	29.3	3.4	4.9	9.6	139.8
Total	2.8	293.5	22.5	25.2	4.1	-17.4	-6.2	49.3	5.3	-25.9	4.8	357.8	
Universal grazing intensification	Cropland: annual crops -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	-3.6	0.0	0.0	-23.7	-24.5	0.0	0.0	-29.7	-2.9	-84.4
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	274.9	0.0	9.9	4.1	4.8	2.8	31.3	2.5	1.3	0.3	334.3
	Grassland -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	-6.1	-10.8	0.0	-3.2	-10.6	-19.1	-6.9	-3.3	-3.9	-63.9
	Grassland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.5	31.8	44.8	27.4	0.0	5.2	28.4	36.5	5.7	4.9	13.9	199.2
Total	3.0	306.7	35.1	26.5	4.1	-16.8	-3.9	48.7	1.4	-26.7	7.3	385.2	
Regrowth case													
No grazing intensification	Cropland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	-12.8	0.0	0.0	-85.6	-80.4	0.0	0.0	-132.1	-13.3	-324.3
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	274.9	0.0	9.9	4.1	4.8	2.8	31.3	2.5	1.3	0.3	334.3
	Grassland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.2	18.6	28.1	16.1	0.0	3.1	18.1	24.1	2.9	3.3	8.6	123.0
	Total	2.8	293.5	15.3	26.0	4.1	-77.7	-59.6	55.4	5.4	-127.5	-4.4	133.0
Grazing intensification on highly productive sites	Cropland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	-12.8	0.0	0.0	-85.6	-80.4	0.0	0.0	-132.1	-13.3	-324.3
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	274.9	0.0	9.9	4.1	4.8	2.8	31.3	2.5	1.3	0.3	334.3
	Grassland -> Vegetation regrowth	-26.5	-617.7	-272.1	-366.9	-40.3	-106.0	-182.6	-483.8	-61.4	-22.8	-95.0	-2275.1
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.1	14.0	28.7	15.0	0.0	4.2	21.2	30.4	2.5	6.8	8.7	131.4
	Total C stock changes	-23.8	-328.8	-256.2	-342.1	-36.2	-182.6	-239.0	-422.2	-56.5	-146.9	-99.3	-2133.7
Universal grazing intensification	Cropland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	-12.8	0.0	0.0	-85.6	-80.4	0.0	0.0	-132.1	-13.3	-324.3
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	274.9	0.0	9.9	4.1	4.8	2.8	31.3	2.5	1.3	0.3	334.3
	Grassland -> Vegetation regrowth	-51.2	-765.8	-468.5	-666.1	-72.0	-124.6	-266.1	-591.7	-89.5	-35.1	-132.4	-3262.9
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.0	16.2	26.7	12.6	0.0	4.8	22.2	33.3	2.5	6.8	8.3	133.5
	Total C stock changes	-48.6	-474.8	-454.6	-643.6	-67.9	-200.6	-321.6	-527.2	-84.5	-159.1	-137.1	-3119.3

Table S19. CO₂ emissions from C stock changes due to land-use change in the scenario BAU with healthy reference diet (annual average emissions during 2012 to 2050 in Mt CO₂e/yr)

Annual average CO ₂ emissions from C stock changes (Mt CO ₂ e/yr)		Northern Africa and Western Asia	Sub-Saharan Africa	Central Asia and Russian Federation	Eastern Asia	Southern Asia	South-east Asia	Northern America	Latin America & the Caribbean	Western Europe	Eastern & South-eastern Europe	Oceania and Australia	World
Bioenergy case													
No grazing intensification	Cropland: annual crops -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	-47.2	-45.8	0.0	-76.7	-104.8	-74.9	-33.4	-58.6	-12.7	-454.1
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	250.3	0.0	0.2	4.1	4.8	2.8	0.8	0.5	1.3	0.3	267.6
	Grassland -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.1	11.4	16.7	9.9	0.0	1.8	10.7	14.7	1.7	2.0	5.1	74.2
Total	2.7	261.7	-30.6	-35.7	4.1	-70.0	-91.2	-59.3	-31.2	-55.4	-7.4	-112.3	
Grazing intensification on highly productive sites	Cropland: annual crops -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	-47.2	-45.8	0.0	-76.7	-104.8	-74.9	-33.4	-58.6	-12.7	-454.1
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	250.3	0.0	0.2	4.1	4.8	2.8	0.8	0.5	1.3	0.3	267.6
	Grassland -> perennial energy crops	0.0	-1.0	-5.7	-4.8	0.0	-3.0	-7.7	-16.0	-0.8	-3.0	-2.7	-44.8
	Grassland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.1	12.0	19.9	13.3	0.0	2.8	15.1	22.1	2.4	4.0	6.4	97.9
Total	2.7	261.2	-33.1	-37.0	4.1	-72.1	-94.5	-67.9	-31.4	-56.4	-8.8	-133.3	
Universal grazing intensification	Cropland: annual crops -> perennial energy crops	0.0	0.0	-47.2	-45.8	0.0	-76.7	-104.8	-74.9	-33.4	-58.6	-12.7	-454.1
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	250.3	0.0	0.2	4.1	4.8	2.8	0.8	0.5	1.3	0.3	267.6
	Grassland -> perennial energy crops	0.0	-1.4	-7.4	-17.3	0.0	-3.9	-12.8	-25.6	-8.9	-4.0	-4.7	-86.1
	Grassland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.5	28.7	38.5	24.8	0.0	4.7	24.3	31.5	5.4	4.2	12.0	174.7
Total	3.0	277.6	-16.2	-38.1	4.1	-71.0	-90.5	-68.1	-36.4	-57.1	-5.2	-97.9	
Regrowth case													
No grazing intensification	Cropland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	-166.3	-214.1	0.0	-277.1	-343.8	-291.5	-144.5	-261.0	-57.9	-1756.1
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	250.3	0.0	0.2	4.1	4.8	2.8	0.8	0.5	1.3	0.3	267.6
	Grassland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.1	11.4	16.7	9.9	0.0	1.8	10.7	14.7	1.7	2.0	5.1	74.2
	Total	2.7	261.7	-149.6	-203.9	4.1	-270.4	-330.3	-276.0	-142.3	-257.7	-52.5	-1414.3
Grazing intensification on highly productive sites	Cropland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	-166.3	-214.1	0.0	-277.1	-343.8	-291.5	-144.5	-261.0	-57.9	-1756.1
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	250.3	0.0	0.2	4.1	4.8	2.8	0.8	0.5	1.3	0.3	267.6
	Grassland -> Vegetation regrowth	-43.6	-1015.6	-447.4	-603.2	-66.2	-174.2	-300.2	-795.5	-101.0	-37.5	-156.2	-3740.7
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.0	8.3	19.1	10.6	0.0	3.4	15.7	25.2	1.5	6.5	5.7	96.1
	Total C stock changes	-41.0	-757.1	-594.6	-806.4	-62.2	-443.0	-625.6	-1061.0	-243.5	-290.7	-208.0	-5133.1
Universal grazing intensification	Cropland -> vegetation regrowth	0.0	0.0	-166.3	-214.1	0.0	-277.1	-343.8	-291.5	-144.5	-261.0	-57.9	-1756.1
	Cropland -> grassland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Grassland -> cropland	2.5	250.3	0.0	0.2	4.1	4.8	2.8	0.8	0.5	1.3	0.3	267.6
	Grassland -> Vegetation regrowth	-52.9	-1094.5	-524.7	-718.5	-78.5	-185.5	-336.3	-854.6	-113.2	-42.6	-173.0	-4174.3
	Change in grazing intensities (all classes)	0.0	9.4	19.0	10.2	0.0	3.7	16.3	26.5	1.7	6.6	5.8	99.3
	Total C stock changes	-50.3	-834.8	-671.9	-922.1	-74.4	-454.0	-661.1	-1118.8	-255.6	-295.8	-224.8	-5563.5

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